

ReCreate

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

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Actor ecosystems and critical actors in precast concrete reuse

Publisher / project	Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy
Project acronym	ReCreate
Deliverable	D7.1 Actor identification and visualized actor maps of critical actors in concrete reuse
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Dissemination level	Public
Cite this document	Harala et al. (2023). <i>Actor ecosystems and critical actors in precast concrete reuse</i> . The ReCreate project.
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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide an understanding on the actor ecosystems and critical actors in the reuse of concrete elements.

To enable the reuse of precast concrete elements, many different actors must collaborate. They include key value chain actors within the construction industry, their subcontractors, and supporting actors, such as authorities. As the reuse of concrete elements provides new challenges and opportunities for the construction industry, it is important to understand the actor ecosystem: the variety of actors, their roles and tasks. Compared to conventional construction projects, the reuse of precast concrete elements requires new skills and new ways of thinking. Therefore, the actors involved have to expand their conventional roles or even take on new roles within the concrete element reuse ecosystem.

The current report provides new understanding on the roles and tasks needed to enable concrete element reuse, and how these tasks can be distributed between the value chain partners. The findings are based on data collected through interviews, ethnographic follow-up and from secondary sources. Related results of the ecosystem mapping have also been published in a journal article and a conference article.

Acknowledgements

The following ReCreate team members helped to visualize the actor ecosystems or supported in validating the actor ecosystems: Ahmad Al-Najjar (KTH), Paul Jonker-Hoffren (TAU) and Mikko Sairanen (TAU).

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1. Introduction

In this report, we have identified and created understanding of the full circular value chain/ecosystem for concrete deconstruction and reuse, with the aim to increase understanding on the critical actors in it. We present the critical actors that are needed to implement the ReCreate value chain commercially including actors directly connected to the project as well as subcontractors and supporting actors. The mappings we present depict the actors and linkages between them, and consequently, the structures of the ecosystems and dynamics within them.

Ecosystems in business contexts refer to networks of interconnected organisations operating around a platform, a focal firm, or a shared objective. In the ReCreate project, the shared objective is concrete element reuse. The ecosystems formed around the country pilots can be considered as circular economy ecosystems. In management research, circular economy ecosystems are defined as a communities of hierarchically independent, yet interdependent heterogeneous actors that collectively generate a sustainable ecosystem outcome (Aarikka-Stenroos et al. 2021a). In ecosystem mapping, the aim is to visualise the ecosystem by connecting the actors, their roles, tasks, and interdependencies according to data gathered from interviews, observations, and reports. Ecosystem mapping enables studying, for example, the value flows, missing linkages, or missing actors in the ecosystem. All in all, ecosystem mapping generates an overall understanding of the actors and their linkages within an ecosystem.

In addition to the work reported herein, a journal article 'Industrial ecosystem renewal towards circularity to achieve the benefits of reuse - Learning from circular construction' (Harala et al., 2023) published in the Journal of Cleaner Production, and a conference article 'Reuse innovation in construction industry: Value creation and the ecosystem' published in the conference proceedings of ISPIM conference (Aarikka-Stenroos et al., 2021b) contribute to the understanding of the critical actors and their tasks and interlinkages in concrete element reuse. We have now studied and depicted three concrete element reuse ecosystems within the ReCreate project (Finland, Sweden and Germany).

2. Methods

Our research data consisted of (1) primary sources, including semi-structured interviews, observations, and ethnographic follow-up, and (2) secondary sources, including media data and reports. Observation and ethnographic follow-up were the most important data collection methods for the pilot projects in Finland and Sweden. They have been undertaken from the beginning of the project (early 2021) onwards. For the pilot project in Germany, interviews provided the main data source, and the site visits supported the understanding gained from the interviews.

The interviews gave us an extensive overview of the roles, tasks, and challenges of individual actors, and the trend of the development in the construction industry. Observation and ethnographic follow-up, on the other hand, gave us a more comprehensive understanding of the actor ecosystems in terms of the linkages between different actors, their interaction, and changes in the roles, interactions, and perceptions resulting from reuse. Moreover, through the interviews we gained insights into micro- and meso-level issues regarding e.g. companies' internal and cooperation challenges due to the new ways of working to enable reusing concrete elements. Through observations and ethnographic follow-up, we were able to identify the interactions between the actors on the meso level, and macro-level issues regarding, for example, legislation affecting the whole industry, and differences between the pilots. The interviewees were chosen because they play central roles in ReCreate's pilot projects and thus provided the most relevant expertise for the actor identification.

We used an abductive reasoning process (Dubois & Gadde, 2002) to analyse the data, and identify and map the actors. We used ecosystem literature (Aarikka-Stenroos & Ritala, 2017; Thomas & Autio, 2020; Aarikka-Stenroos et al., 2021a) to map the ecosystems, taking a somewhat deductive approach, while a data-driven thematic analysis undertaken in a more inductive manner provided findings on the interlinkages between the actors, the reuse process, and the tasks. We utilised thematic and content analysis (Mayring, 2004) to analyse the data. For example, in the data analysis, the statement *'we help in everything we can, and we learn from it at the same time. Because there are no clear roles [in concrete element reuse], unlike in conventional construction'* by an architect interviewee was interpreted to explain the role changes of the ecosystem actors needed to enable concrete element reuse.

We initiated the data analysis with a within-case analysis of each pilot to map and visualise the actor ecosystems of the different pilots separately. After first analysing the actor maps of the pilots separately, we then compared them through a cross-case analysis to improve the interpretations of the actor ecosystems by e.g. identifying if some roles or tasks were missing from another pilot and if so, why.

3. Identified actors and visualised actor maps

3.1 Overview of the ReCreate pilots in Finland, Sweden and Germany

Table 1 displays the actors in the Finnish, Swedish, and German pilots. In it, each actor has been assigned with an identified role and a description what the role entails in the context of concrete element reuse. More detailed visual descriptions of the pilot projects in Finland (3.2), Sweden (3.3) and Germany (3.4) are presented in later dedicated sections.

Since at the time of writing, only the Swedish pilot has completed all the work related to reusing concrete elements, some of the actors in the Finnish and German pilot projects are still unknown. They are therefore described as TBA (to be announced), i.e., a specific actor is not yet known and will be specified as the project progresses. Other abbreviations used refer to the universities involved in the pilots, i.e. TAU = Tampere University, KTH = Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan / Royal Institute of Technology, and BTU = Brandenburgische Technische Universität / Brandenburg University of Technology. In addition, if a role is not identified in the pilot, it is marked as “Not applicable”.

Table 1. An overview of the different pilots and generalisation of the roles in concrete element reuse.

Role:	Pilot projects:			Description of the roles for concrete element reuse:
	Finland	Sweden	Germany	
Owner of the building to be constructed	TBA	Helsingborgshem & Wihlborgs fastigheter	Wohnungbaugesellschaft Hohenmölsen (WOBAU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decision making regarding the characteristics of the building(s) to be constructed of reused elements. - Funding (potential financier of the building to be constructed).
Construction company	Skanska (project partner)	Skanska (Swedish sister company, not project partner)	Ecosoil Ost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Construction of the new building(s). -Applying for demolition (If the actor is the owner of the donor building) and building permits. -Work safety planning (reuse). -Logistics planning. -Supporting roles in other project phases, e.g., quality assurance and testing, deconstruction planning, and redesign.
Structural engineering company	Ramboll	Skanska (in-house) & Tyréns	P. Jähne Ingenieurbüro & Circular Structural Design (CSD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building condition survey and quality assurance of building components. - Taking part in deconstruction planning (structural aspects). - Redesign (structural aspects). - Taking part in the planning of refurbishment (structural aspects). - Taking part in inventorying the building to be deconstructed.
Demolition company	Umacon	Trellegräv & Wigrens	Ecosoil Ost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Deconstruction of the building(s). -Deconstruction planning (work- and equipment-related aspects). -Work safety planning (deconstruction). -Taking part in logistics planning.
Architecture company	Liike	Fojab & KTH	Jochen Dreetz & TBA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Redesign (architectural aspects) -Taking part in inventorying the building to be deconstructed.
Manufacturing company	Parma	Strängbetong	Ecosoil Ost (not a manufacturer, but takes on these tasks)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Refurbishing deconstructed elements. - Potentially providing interim storage and tagging/tracing elements. - Supporting roles in other project phases, e.g., safety, logistics, and deconstruction planning, redesign.
City	City of Tampere	City of Helsingborg	City of Hohenmölsen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permitting (e.g., demolition permit, building permit). - Enabling circular construction solutions in the city as a forerunner (e.g., streamlining bureaucracy procedures and supporting other actors in them, taking CE principles into account for example in land-use planning and land sales/rentals).
University	TAU	KTH	BTU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinating the country pilots in ReCreate project → Universities do not take part in conventional construction projects. -Knowledge creation, facilitation, and dissemination.

3.2 Pilot project in Finland

Figure 1 gives a description of the Finnish pilot and its phases. Figure 2 describes the Finnish pilot ecosystem. The ecosystem (Figure 2) displays (1) the actors involved in the reuse of precast concrete elements, (2) the activities needed to reuse precast concrete elements, and (3) how the actors are interlinked.

Figure 1. Description of the Finnish pilot project process.

Figure 2. The ecosystem of the Finnish pilot project.

3.3 Pilot project in Sweden

Figure 3 presents a description of the pilot process in Sweden and Figure 4 gives a description of the Swedish pilot ecosystem. The ecosystem (Figure 4) displays (1) the actors involved in the reuse of precast concrete elements, (2) the activities needed to reuse precast concrete elements, and (3) how the actors are interlinked.

Figure 3. Description of Swedish pilot project process. Notes: Municipal waste facility NSR stored the wall elements. The forging constructor designed the steel connections between the beams and columns.

Figure 4. The ecosystem of the Swedish pilot project.

3.4 Pilot project in Germany

Figure 5 shows the process and phases of the German pilot, and Figure 6 displays the actor ecosystem of (1) the actors involved in the reuse of precast concrete elements, (2) the activities needed to reuse precast concrete elements, (3) and how the actors are interlinked.

Figure 5. The pilot project process in Germany.

Figure 6. The ecosystem of the pilot project in Germany.

4. Conclusion

This report provided an overview of the critical actors for concrete reuse. We utilised qualitative methods to map the ecosystems and processes of the pilots for the pilots in Finland, Sweden, and Germany. The main findings of the actor mapping displays that the task division can differ across the actors in different pilot. Nevertheless, the ecosystem has to cover the full value chain, and sharing expertise among the ecosystem actors is critical. All the pilots include approximately the same process phases, yet there are differences in the actor settings. The tasks can be divided to an extensive ecosystem of construction industry actors, such as in the Finnish pilot or the ecosystem can entail a smaller number of key actors who take care of the tasks with subcontractors, such as in the Swedish pilot. To conclude, concrete elements can be successfully reused via multiple ecosystem compositions as long as the expertise and competences of the actor ecosystem are able to cover all the necessary tasks and process phases.

References Aarikka-Stenroos, L., & Ritala, P. (2017). Network management in the era of ecosystems: Systematic review and management framework. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 67: 23–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.08.010>

Aarikka-Stenroos, L., Ritala, P., Thomas, L.D.W., (2021a). Circular economy ecosystems: a typology, definitions, and implications. In: Teerikangas, S., Onkila, T., Koistinen, K., Makela, M. (Eds.), *Research Handbook of Sustainability Agency*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 257–273.

Aarikka-Stenroos, L., Alkki, L., Harala, L., & Riuttala, M. (2021b). Reuse innovation in construction industry: Value creation and the ecosystem. In: *ISPIM Conference Proceedings*, 1–21. The International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM). Manchester.

Dubois, A., & Gadde, L. E. (2002). Systematic combining: An abductive approach to case research. *Journal of Business Research*, 55(7), 553–560.

Harala, L., Alkki, L., Aarikka-Stenroos, L., Al-Najjar, A., & Malmqvist, T. (2023). Industrial ecosystem renewal towards circularity to achieve the benefits of reuse—Learning from circular construction. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.135885>

Mayring, P. (2004). Qualitative content analysis. *A companion to qualitative research*, 1(2), 159–176.

Thomas, L. D. W., & Autio, E. (2020). Innovation ecosystems in management: An organizing typology. In: *Oxford research encyclopaedia of business and management*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.